

UNDERTREES: Creating knowledge for UNDERstanding ecosystem seRvicEs of agroforESty systems through a holistic methodological framework

UNDERTREES

AGROFORESTRY RESEARCH

Deliverable D1.1 – Data Management Plan

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Author(s):	Simona Bosco, Alberto Mantino, Giorgio Ragaglini, Barbara Pucci (SSSA)
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Legend

Acronym	Definition
CA	Consortium Agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (research data)
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
ORD	Open Research Data pilot
PC	Project Coordinator
PMB	Project Management Board

1. Definitions

Dataset: Digital information created during research, but which is not a published research output. Research data excludes purely administrative records. The highest priority research data is that which underpins a research output. Research data do not include publications, articles, lectures or presentations.

Data Management Plan (DMP): A formal working document which outlines how datasets will be handled both during the active research phase and after the project is completed. DMPs are now a requirement of a research grant proposals and therefore must be addressed at the earliest phase of the research lifecycle.

Digital Object Identifier (DOI): A persistent identifier for a document that can be handled by a resolution service to direct communications to the correct server. Developed by the International DOI Foundation (www.doi.org).

Metadata: Information about datasets stored in a repository/database template. A text document's metadata may contain information about how long the document is, who the author is, when the document was written, and a short summary of the document.

Repository: A digital repository is a mechanism for managing and storing digital content. Repositories can be subject or institutional in their focus.

Zenodo: a research output publication and archival service built and developed by researchers from the CERN IT department, to ensure that everyone can join in Open Science. Based on the open source Invenio digital library framework, Zenodo was created through the OpenAIRE project and is hosted at CERN (<https://zenodo.org/>).

2. Introduction

This report describes the Initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the UNDERTREES project, funded by the EU’s Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement number 872384.

The purpose of the DMP is to set out the main elements of the UNDERTREES consortium data management policy for the datasets generated by the project. The DMP will present in detail only the procedure for the management of datasets created during the lifetime of the project and describes the key data management principles, notably in terms of data standards and metadata, sharing, archiving and preservation.

The Data Management Plan of UNDERTREES is articulated around the following key points:

- I. This Data Management Plan (DMP) has been prepared by considering the template of the “Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020”.¹

The DMP is an official project Deliverable (D1.1) due in Month 36 (December 2022), but it will be a live document throughout the project. This initial version will evolve depending on significant changes arising and periodic reviews at reporting stages of the project.

- II. The consortium will comply with the requirements of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR). Guidance on how these regulations interact with open-access data policy can be found here: <https://www.openaire.eu/ordp/>

- III. Type of data, storage, confidentiality, ownership, management of intellectual property and access: Procedures that will be implemented for data collection, storage, access, sharing policies, protection, retention and destruction will be in line with EU standards as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, particularly Articles 18, Keeping Records – Supporting Documentation; Article 23, Management of Intellectual Property; Article 24 Agreement on background; Article 25, Access Rights to Background; Article 26, Ownership of Results; Article 27, Protection of Results – Visibility of EU funding; Article 30, Transfer and Licensing of Results; Article 31, Access Rights to Results; Article 36, Confidentiality; Article 37 Security-related Obligations; Article 39 Processing of Personal Data; Article 52, Communication between the parties, and “Annex I – Description of Work” of the Grant Agreement.

UNDERTREES will generate diverse outputs, including measurement data, observations, validation protocols, survey results, interview recordings and scientific articles relating to the assessment of the ecosystem services of agroforestry systems at field, landscape and policy level.

This diversity requires a Data Management Plan, building on existing open science resources that are interoperable and trusted.

Annex 1 - Data Inventory Table, included in the DMP, is a comprehensive description of UNDERTREES datasets. Like the DMP, this Annex will evolve and grow over the course of the project.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

3. Data Summary

The purpose of data generation and collection is to create a shared knowledge on agroforestry ecosystem services for European agricultural policy development. To do that several types of data will be generated and collected within three thematic areas (1) agronomic and environmental sustainability, (2) socio-economic sustainability and (3) policy development. The organization of data collection and most convenient format will be the responsibility of the relevant task leader and will be integrated in a secure platform (Microsoft Teams) managed by Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna (SSSA).

A detailed description of the type and format of UNDERTREES data that will be generated and collected can be found in Annex 1 - Data Inventory Table. Table 1 presents a short summary of the 27 datasets that have been identified for UNDERTREES (listed by Dataset number and Task number) (update December 2022).

Table 1: Dataset collected or generated in UNDERTREES.

WP	Task	Task lead	Dataset N°	Dataset Description
WP1	1.3	SSSA	1	Data on secondment quality
WP2	2.3	SSSA	2	Data on staff feedback from training activities
WP3	3.1	SSSA	3	Methodological framework for the assessment of ES at field scale
	3.2	UEX	4	Living Lab database
	3.3	SSSA	5	Data collected at field site UK1
	3.3	SSSA	6	Data collected at field site UK2
	3.3	SSSA	7	Data collected at field site ES1
	3.3	SSSA	8	Data collected at field site ES2
	3.3	SSSA	9	Data collected at field site IT1
	3.3	SSSA	10	Data collected at field site IT2
	3.3	SSSA	11	Data collected at field site GH1
	3.3	SSSA	12	Data collected at field site GH2
	3.3	SSSA	13	Data collected at field site GH3
	3.3	SSSA	14	Data collected at field site TZ1
	3.3	SSSA	15	Data collected at field site TZ2
	3.3	SSSA	16	Data collected at field site CL1
	3.3	SSSA	17	Data collected at field site CL2
	WP4	4.1	UEX	21
4.2		UEX/VEX	22	Agro-environmental modelling for ES assessment
4.3		CAWR/USC	23	Socio-economic modelling for ES assessment
4.4		AFBI	24	Integrated sustainability at landscape level
WP5	5.1	USC	25	Stakeholder network
	5.2	USC/CAWR	26	Survey data from stakeholder consultation
	5.3	SSSA/USC	27	Data on local action plan

As the project progresses and data is identified and collected, further information on the specific dataset will be outlined in subsequent versions of the DMP. Additional datasets may be identified and added to future versions of the DMP as necessary.

4. FAIR Principles in UNDERTREES

UNDERTREES participates in the Open Research Data (ORD) pilot and aims to make data open whenever possible, but as closed as necessary when taking into consideration personal data and privacy. Where it affects personal confidentiality and privacy, data will not be shared publicly. UNDERTREES will work to ensure that its data will be “FAIR”, that is findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable, according to the point below.

4. 1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

UNDERTREES, as part of the ORD Pilot, is expected to deposit generated and collected data in an open online research data repository. UNDERTREES has selected the ZENODO repository as its data. ZENODO is an OpenAIRE and CERN collaboration that allows researchers to deposit both publications and data, providing tools to linking them to these through persistent identifiers and data citations. ZENODO is set up to facilitate the finding, accessing, re-using and interoperating of data sets, which are the basic principles that ORD projects must comply with. The guidelines provided by ZENODO will be used by UNDERTREES to ensure the right format of data is uploaded to comply with FAIR principles.

Other online research data repositories will be considered depending on data types and formats generated and collected data. Beneficiaries will be encouraged to consider the Registry of Research Data Repositories and Databib and Directory of Open Access Repositories (OpenDOAR) for useful listings of repositories that might be suitable for UNDERTREES outputs.

The protocol below outlines the management principles behind storing and making findable data collected through the UNDERTREES.

PROTOCOL – Storing UNDERTREES data and making it 'Findable'

Beneficiaries will follow these processes for each dataset collected or generated through the UNDERTREES project:

- Store and make findable any UNDERTREES data that can be made openly accessible (see next section), either in the ZENODO repository or in another online data repository suitable for the type and format of data generated or collected. Any chosen online repository needs to facilitate identification of data and refer to standard identification mechanisms (ideally persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers), which should be outlined.
- Ensure that research outputs and datasets are cross-referencing each other (e.g. scientific publications and the data behind them).
- Outline the discoverability of the data (give metadata provision).
- The organisation, data collection and most convenient format will be under the responsibility of the relevant task leader.

- Each task leader will be responsible for depositing relevant data in Zenodo or another appropriate open-access online repository. Data will be made accessible within six months of publishing the data in peer-reviewed scientific articles or similar, unless beneficiaries have outlined justifiable reasons for maintaining data confidentiality (see section 3.3 for further details).
- Each beneficiary is responsible for their records and documentation in relation to data generated, which must be in line with the accepted standards in the respective field, overseen by Task Leaders. To avoid losses, beneficiaries must take measures to ensure that data is backed-up using reliable methods.
- All **deliverables** will be named in line with the following template: **UNDERTREES_Partner_WP#_DX.X._Title_vXX**. Partner is the abbreviation of the partner institution (e.g. SSSA), WP# indicates the work package number (e.g. WP1), DX.X indicates the deliverable number (e.g. D1.2), and title is the name given to the deliverable or data package by the responsible WP leader. Finally, all documents and data are assigned a version number.
- All **datasets** will be named in line with the following template: **UNDERTREES_Partner_WP#_description_number**. Partner is the abbreviation of the partner institution (e.g. SSSA) and WP# indicates the work package number (e.g. WP1). Finally, all datasets are assigned a description of the type of data and a progressive number for the same dataset.
- In conjunction with the release of data on Zenodo, all WP leaders will provide metadata on data packages generated and respectively curated within their respective WP. Each generated data will be described with metadata to allow discovery, analysis and support effective data sharing.
- As a general rule and as possible, UNDERTREES will use general and disciplinary standards for describing data (see the Research Data Alliance Metadata standards Directory²) according to the following categories:
 - Descriptive metadata, e.g., title, subject, description, key words, etc;
 - Technical and structural metadata, e.g., format, date, size, schema, etc;
 - Administrative metadata (e.g. owner, ownership rights, right to use, access right, responsible, data retention, embargo period, etc.)

Metadata vocabularies that have been identified to-date for UNDERTREES datasets are listed in Annex 1: Data Inventory Table. As the project progresses and data is identified and collected, further information on metadata and making data findable will be outlined in subsequent versions of the DMP. Information on naming conventions used, approach towards search keywords, approach for clear versioning, and specification of standards for metadata creation (if any) will also be provided. Final versions of documents and deliverables are published on the project website. Previous and working document versions are stored on the UNDERTREES project platform on Microsoft Teams to which all partners have secure data access.

² <http://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/>

4.2. Making data openly accessible

Within UNDERTREES, the data from experimental and demonstration activities will be used to validate the methodologies developed for ecosystem services assessment in agroforestry systems at field and landscape scale and to inform about this new approach and its results. Data from field sites (WP3) will feed landscape modelling of ecosystem services in WP4, moreover data created in WP3 and WP4 will feed work in WP5 where a multi-actor approach and local plan will be developed.

To maximise the impact of UNDERTREES data, the project will facilitate sharing of results and deliverables within and beyond the consortium. Selected data and results will be shared with the scientific community and other stakeholders through publications in scientific journals and presentations at conferences, as well as through open-access data repositories. There will be an open access policy applied to these following the rules outlined in the Grant and Consortium Agreements.

Task leaders will collect data from each task and each WP leader together with task leaders will review and approve all data that is identified as appropriate for open access. This process will be carried out on an ongoing basis to facilitate the publication of appropriate data as soon as possible. All data will be made available for verification and re-use, unless the task leader can justify why data cannot be made openly accessible.

The review and approval of each dataset at task and WP level will avoid any possible conflicts between open access and IPR issues. In any case, the PMB is responsible for the IPR issues within UNDERTREES.

Where it is determined that a database should be kept confidential, the reasons for doing so will be included in an updated version of the DMP. Table 2 illustrates the expected levels of accessibility of UNDERTREES data.

Table 2: Level of accessibility of UNDERTREES datasets.

Dataset N°	WP	Task	Description	Open/restricted	Reason for restriction
1	1	1.3	Data on secondment quality	Restricted	GDPR
2	2	2.3	Staff feedback from training activities and secondments	Restricted	GDPR
3	3	3.1	Methodology framework for the assessment of ES at field scale	Open	NA
4	3	3.2	Living Lab database	Open	NA
5	3	3.3	Data collected at field site UK1	Open	NA
6	3	3.3	Data collected at field site UK2	Open	NA
7	3	3.3	Data collected at field site ES1	Open	NA
8	3	3.3	Data collected at field site ES2	Open	NA
9	3	3.3	Data collected at field site IT1	Open	NA
10	3	3.3	Data collected at field site IT2	Open	NA
11	3	3.3	Data collected at field site GH1	Open	NA
12	3	3.3	Data collected at field site GH2	Open	NA
13	3	3.3	Data collected at field site GH3	Open	NA
14	3	3.3	Data collected at field site TZ1	Open	NA

15	3	3.3	Data collected at field site TZ2	Open	NA
16	3	3.3	Data collected at field site CL1	Open	NA
17	3	3.3	Data collected at field site CL2	Open	NA
18	3	3.3	Data collected at field site CL3	Open	NA
19	3	3.3	Data collected at field site EC1	Open	NA
20	3	3.3	Data collected at field site Ec2	Open	NA
21	4	4.1	Methodology framework for the assessment of ES at landscape scale	Open	NA
22	4	4.2	Agro-environmental modelling for ES assessment	Open	NA
23	4	4.3	Socio-economic modelling for ES assessment	Open	NA
24	4	4.4	Integrated sustainability at landscape level	Open	NA
25	5	5.1	Stakeholder network	Open	NA
26	5	5.2	Survey data from stakeholder consultation	Restricted	GDPR
27	5	5.3	Data on local action plan	Open	NA

Protocol: Making UNDERTREES Data Openly Accessible

- To encourage re-use and further application of project results, all UNDERTREES data that underlies scientific publications will be made available via open-access online platforms, unless subject to protection or if the achievement of the action's main objective would be jeopardised by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible (Art. 29 GA).
- Data that results from UNDERTREES activities that underlies scientific publications must be submitted to the relevant Task Leader and WP leader not more than 10 days following any related publication in scientific journals (unless data is subject to protection or embargo periods). Upon receipt of data, the WP leader and the task leader will evaluate each dataset and request additions or modifications in a timely manner, to facilitate the upload of the dataset by task leaders no more than 30 days after the original date of publication. It is the responsibility of project partners to prepare the submission in a timely manner to facilitate this process.
- All UNDERTREES data collection should be completed prior to the official deadline (Art 29 of GA). Partners are expected to observe such deadlines and have all data in a suitable format ready for sharing openly according to these deadlines unless the publications have not yet been accepted.
- When considering the potential to make data open access, Partners are requested to review the project Consortium Agreement which follows the standard rules as outlined in the DESCA model (<http://www.desca-2020.eu/>) for Horizon 2020. This defines the main approach regarding the ownership, protection and access to key knowledge like IPR and data. This approach will allow the UNDERTREES partners, collectively and individually, to pursue market opportunities arising from the project's results. Some of the major aspects covered are briefly indicated below:
- **Confidentiality:** Each partner will treat information from other partners as confidential unless otherwise stated and not disclose it to third parties unless the information is publicly available.

- **Open access to publications:** Any proposed publication or communication by one of the parties is required to be submitted to other beneficiaries for their consent, according to CA Article 8.4.2.1. All publications will be either gold or green open access in accordance with the H2020 requirements.
- **Open access to Data:** Task leaders will notify the partnership of their planned intent to upload datasets to open-access repositories following approval of data for such purpose by the PMB.
- **Pre-existing know how:** Each partner is and remains the sole owner of its IPR over its pre-existing know-how. The partners will identify and list in the Consortium Agreement and DMP the Pre-Existing Know-How over which they may grant access rights for the project. The partners agree that the Access Rights to the Pre-existing Know-How needed for carrying out their own work under the project shall be granted on a royalty-free basis.
- **Ownership and protection of Foreground:** The ownership of foreground will belong to the partner/s generating it. Protection will be done appropriately. When the Foreground is the result of a work carried out by two or more partners and their respective share of the work cannot be ascertained, joint ownership will be agreed between the partners as it is established in the Consortium Agreement. If a partner wishes to assign any knowledge to a third party he should do so, while observing the conditions set out in Articles 26 and 30 of the UNDERTREES Grant Agreement, and should inform the other partners and request their consent, which should not unreasonably be withheld.
- **Access Rights:** Partners grant to each other royalty-free access right to knowledge generated in the project and to the background knowledge they bring to the project to the extent needed to successfully perform the project tasks allocated to them.
- **Patents:** Under Article 27.1 of the Grant Agreement, partners who own knowledge suitable for patent are obliged to make applications for patents or similar form of protection and shall supply details of such application to the other partners. Information relating to patents that have been registered must be submitted under the 'IPR' section of the EU Participant Portal.
- **Use and dissemination:** If dissemination of knowledge does not adversely affect its protection or use and subject to legitimate interests, the partners shall ensure further dissemination of their own knowledge as provided under the Grant Agreement (see Article 29) and the Consortium Agreement (see Section 8.4) which has been signed by all partners.

As the project progresses and data is identified and collected, further information on making data openly accessible will be outlined in subsequent versions of the DMP. In specific, information on methods or software tools needed to access the data, information on where data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited and how access will be provided in case there are restrictions.

4.3. Making data interoperable

Partners will observe OpenAIRE guidelines for online interoperability, including OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories, OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives, OpenAIRE Guidelines for CRIS Managers based on CERIF-XML. These guidelines can be found at: <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>. Partners will also ensure that UNDERTREES data observes FAIR data principles under H2020 open-access policy³.

Information related to the interoperability of UNDERTREES datasets has been collected in Annex 1 - Data Inventory Table. As the project progresses and data is identified and collected, further information on making data interoperable will be outlined in subsequent versions of the DMP. In specific, information on data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodology to follow to facilitate interoperability and whether the project uses standard vocabulary for all data types present to allow interdisciplinary interoperability.

4.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

UNDERTREES is expected to produce a substantial volume of novel data and knowledge through experimental approaches that will be presented to the scientific community, industry, policy-makers and society at large through a carefully designed portfolio of dissemination actions. Datasets uploaded in the ZENODO repository will be freely accessible after an embargo period determined per dataset, if required. Copyright of the data are based on EU H2020 guidelines and on the principles of the Digital Curation Centre (DCC), an internationally recognised centre of expertise in digital curation with a focus on building capability and skills for research data management.

Access to the research data will be dependent on any agreed 'embargo period' based on national and EU regulations. The 'embargo period' is applied to allow time for work to be published or seek patents, were applicable. This time will be as short as possible until the work is accepted for publication or patent, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Data will be stored based on the contractual terms, until which it can be reusable (all research related data will be stored for at least for five years after the end of the research project). Due to the combined natural and social science nature of the data there is no time limit for its re-usability. In the case of sharing data or restricting certain data with third parties outside of the consortium, a data sharing agreement will be set up that will detail anonymising or aggregating data, participant consent for data sharing, copyright permissions, and agreement on any embargo periods. Data will be used in standard forms allowing reuse, as well as allowing searchability.

As the project progresses and data is identified and collected, further information on increasing data re-use will be outlined in subsequent versions of the DMP. In specific, information on how data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible, when the data will be made available for re-use, whether

³ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, a description of data quality assurance processes and specifications of length of time for which the data will remain re-usable will be provided.

5. Quality assurance

Data quality is the responsibility of the respective WP leaders. Assurance of high quality is maintained by transparency of methods, and open access to generated data and documentation.

The quality assurance of the UNDERTREES project deliverables is achieved by a two-step peer-reviewed mechanism: in the first step the PMB provides comments and feedback, while in the second step one reviewing partner checks the final quality of the deliverable.

6. Allocation of resources

Costs related to open-access to research data in Horizon 2020 are eligible for reimbursement under the conditions defined in the H2020 Grant Agreement, in particular Article 6 and Article 6.2.D.3, but also other articles relevant for the cost category chosen. Costs cannot be claimed retrospectively. Project beneficiaries will be responsible for applying for reimbursement for costs related to making data accessible to others beyond the consortium.

Financing for data storage and making data available after the life of the project is covered by the project in-direct costs for each partner and for the lead partner Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna. The costs for ongoing maintenance of the repositories will be met by Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna.

The DMP applies to all UNDERTREES research of all consortium partners (academics and non-academics) and individually each researcher or research team employed or subcontracted will be responsible for managing their data adequately. Where UNDERTREES researchers plan to publish with co-authors outside of UNDERTREES, they will make them aware of the UNDERTREES DMP requirements and data collection procedures and make sure that primary research data are stored to the same standard as required for H2020 projects.

Responsibility for this will be with the first author. The minimum requirement is to store the final data set that was used for publication. With the UNDERTREES project, the project coordinator and the PMB will take overall responsibility for data management within the project.

7. Data security

UNDERTREES data will be stored in a certified repository (Microsoft Teams), also for long term preservation and curation.

Security and timely deletion of locally stored sensitive data is the responsibility of the relevant WP leader.

The secure Microsoft Teams platform constitutes the primary storage for data, including non-anonymised data. Partners will safely handle and store data locally immediately in relation to data collection / cleaning / analyses. When these are transferred to Microsoft Teams folders, data will be deleted from local systems."

Each partner organisation is responsible for complying with the general data protection regulation (GDPR) when collecting data within the WPs that they participate in.

The following data will be stored:

- Data used in publications (sample copies of records used to collect information, analysed research data, supporting documents);
- Data required by involved partners/funding agencies (records of procedures (es. Protocols) and records relating to the financial management of the project (PDF invoices, any other supporting account records);
- Data that might be used in future research: interim reports, final reports, drafts of manuscript in academic or applied farmer-facing literature.

Subject to adherence to any restrictions arising from the need for compliance with GDPR and ethical consent procedures (e.g. respondent anonymity) the following types of data will be stored:

- Original data e.g. video and audio recordings, hard copy and digital surveys, paper or digital experimental records;
- Raw data, e.g. unprocessed digital data, site measurement data, plant and soil samples, digital audio, photographic or video recordings;
- Processed data sets used in publications, including information used to understand the processing, in particular coding steps, data cleaning logs, missing values, metadata for each data set
- Where applicable, Intermediate data sets to guarantee transparency and scientific integrity of data processing
- Data sharing agreements

Access to electronic data and records is controlled by passwords and, where appropriate, access to individual files folder or databases will also be password protected. Passwords will be known only by authorised individuals. Access controls will be reviewed regularly and updated as individuals join, leave or change roles within the project. Computers and software will not be left logged in and unattended. Digital data will normally be stored in the format in which they were generated. The project shared repository on the Microsoft Teams App is hosted by Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna. Access is limited to authorised individuals with passwords.

8. Ethical aspects

All partners will assure that the EU standards regarding ethics and data management are fulfilled. More details in relation to Ethics (and Security) in relation to Data Management can be found in Annex 1 – Part B Section 6 of the Grant Agreement.

Any risks concerning personal data protection are mitigated by the following measures which have been adopted by design to ensure fairness in the human being involvement:

- **Fairness & Confidentiality:** data protection policies applied to the project include pseudonymization of personal data as well as specific confidential obligations for the researchers involved in the project. This will ensure that individuals fundamental rights may not be affected by the participation of the project.
- **Fairness & data quality:** results will be published only as aggregated ones, considering proper thresholds. Answers will never re-associated to individuals. If group vulnerabilities are identified, results related to the specific ground of discrimination will not be communicated.
- **Fairness & transparency:** participation is voluntary: as stated in the informed consent sheet (see: Annex 1 – Part B Section 6 of the Grant Agreement), at any stage of the project participants may ask for further explanation and information, withdraw without the obligation to justify the reasons. This will ensure autonomy of each choice.

The results of the so called ethical-impact assessment will be updated whenever required by the technical development of the project (Task 1.3), as a living document of the project. This will ensure an accountable management of the ethical issues, including the ones concerning data protection.

Informed consent will be secured from all human participants when participating in any primary data collection activities within the UNDERTREES project (for example, surveys, focus groups and citizen juries) and an information sheet will explain any potential risks that might be involved (for example being identified as part of a particular group or providing personal information by chance) and how confidentiality will be ensured throughout the collection, analysis and dissemination of data. All participants will take part in the research voluntarily and can decide at any moment to discontinue their participation. Informed consent will be secured from all human participants.

The information sheet will also provide information on how and who to contact regarding any further questions about the project. The information will be explained in person at the start of each new data collection activity, after which the participants will be asked to sign an informed consent form indicating their consent to participate in the research. All participants are informed that they can withdraw their consent for whatever reason they wish, by an agreed deadline (or at any point, if they are identifiable). Permission will be sought to digitally record data collection activities (audio, visual, creative drawn image-based capture, or to record them in writing), explaining that all possible steps will be taken to ensure confidentiality and anonymity of participants at the level of the individual (unless participants specifically request otherwise). Templates of the informed consent and information sheet forms will be kept on file.

9. UNDERTREES’S DMP Review Process & Timetable

This first version of the UNDERTREES DMP will be validated by the PMB and will function as the operational manual until a next update has been validated. The DMP will be updated with the delivery of periodic reports (M48: December 2023 and M66: June 2026). The DMP will be updated over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise, such as:

- New data
- Changes in consortium policies
- Changes in consortium composition and external factors

10. References

- Data Management in the context of Horizon 2020:
http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm
- Guidelines on the Implementation of Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Projects supported by the European Research Council under Horizon 2020
https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/hi/oa-pilot/h2020-hi-erc-oa-guide_en.pdf
- FAIR data principles (FORCE11 discussion forum)
<https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>
- The Open Research Data (ORD) Pilot in H2020:
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- FAQs on research data management and open research data
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- Ethics self-assessment under Horizon 2020:
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- European Intellectual Property HelpDesk
<https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/>
- Registry of Research Data Repositories
<https://www.re3data.org/>
- Metadata Standards Directory of
<http://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/>
- OpenAIRE repository:
<https://www.openaire.eu/opendatapilot-dmp>
- Zenodo:
<https://zenodo.org>
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